

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIMEDIA MATERIALS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES. THE ANALYSIS OF ARTICLE.

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Abstract: This paper is devoted to the analysis of an article and its comparison with other courses in teaching field. The name of the article is called "Multimedia materials in developing countries: The Malaysian English language teaching (ELT) experience" which was written by Jayakaran Mukundan. The reader read it, write summary and comments concerning it, evaluate it and compare it with other related courses. By analyzing the article, the reader explains the effectiveness of usage of multimedia materials in Malaysia.

Key vocabulary: ELT, evaluation, comment, effectiveness, multimedia materials.

1. Summary of chosen article.

The chosen article: Multimedia materials in developing countries: Malaysian English language teaching (ELT) experience was written by Jayakaran Mukundan in 2008. The article gives information concerning the application of multimedia materials in Malaysian education system and shows the results of the attempts. Bandwagon theory is considered the psychological phenomenon of humans to love trends. Like other developing countries Malaysia also loves to imitate developed countries' trends and tried to change trends in fashion by implementing new multimedia materials in the education system. According to some rush reasons: the notion "Vision 2020" which belongs to developed countries was used by Malaysia to implement computers and computer technology at all levels, "Smart schools" development emphasized education by using computers to develop multimedia, increased number of a large middle class and their attempts to buy personal computers for the home and using English in Mathematics and Science teaching with the help of new policy, multimedia was implemented in different fields together with education.

However, some misconceptions about multimedia usage in ELT led the Malaysian education system to over-indulgence and provided wrong signals for people in education. Firstly, they equipped language classrooms with a row of computers like laboratory by misunderstanding as a result, learners accessed computers individually by playing language programs and teachers played the role of laboratory assistant. Secondly, the creation of "Teaching courseware" led

all Malaysian companies to create a custom-made courseware for schools from English, Mathematics and Science. As a result, there was a competition between textbooks and courseware usage and teachers as an orchestra conductor demonstrated courseware menus and conducted activities. The last misconception was that they believed about implementing teaching courseware can bring profit and suitable for language teaching pedagogy. Unfortunately, teachers only clicked the courseware and demonstrated the weekly routine of the content program this is because they were not involved in the teaching procedure. In addition, the courseware more practiced learners with testing than teaching and the LCD projector was switched on during the lesson and it was not seemed unnatural for authority.

Section 2. Evaluation of the article.

The article was written in a logical order and it starts with giving a notion about Bandwagon and its connection with education and multimedia. Then, it follows with the reasons of implementing multimedia tools in education and some misconceptions about implementation of the tools with the harmful results of the attempts in education. Despite it has logical order among subtopics which leads the learner to understand the ideas smoothly, it presents very limited citations which can be proof for the author's ideas and facts. Because it is very difficult to believe and come to mind about a country's bringing multimedia in education and its results by leaning only on an author's facts and points. Moreover, the reader thinks that it would be better if the author gave some directions for the implementation of multimedia materials in a profitable ways since she understood the reasons and results of multimedia implementation at developing countries' level but she couldn't get know about the best implementation ways and results of multimedia in developed countries which is considered effective and fill the gap between best implementation ways and incorrect ones. However, by reading the article the reader compared the procedure with her own country and it helped her how to analyze the same procedure in her country's education field and helped also for understand current attempts and their inevitable results.

The connection of the article with other courses.

While reading the article the reader leaned on her previous knowledge which she learned from other courses and materials and they helped her to understand every single point of the article fully. The article's data connects ideas with SLA, CD, Grammar for ESL/EFL teachers, Language planning and policy courses. Because while teaching SLA, ESL, EFL, Grammar we as teachers should pay

attention to every usage of multimedia carefully so as not to repeat the misconceptions of the Malaysian experience. Moreover, there are some articles and their ideas are connected with this article. Especially from the Grammar for ESL/EFL Teachers' course material: "Using original videos and sound effects to teach English" by Shahla Yassaei helped her a lot to comprehend the article (by Mukundan) effectively because the whole article devoted to the effective usage of different multimedia types. With the help of the article by Shahla Yassaei, the reader got know about how the implementation of multimedia in the Malaysian education system was used ineffectively when recall the ways of effective implementation of multimedia in the language classrooms. Furthermore, Language Planning and Policy course and its articles led her to understand how and why micro-level and macro-level policies attituded wrongly regarding the multimedia implementation in Malaysian education system. She can give sample articles from the course as well: "Macro language planning» by Kaplan, "Micro language plans" by Kheng and Baldauf etc.

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